

NORWEGIAN PARTICIPATION AND CONTRIBUTION TO THE EUROPEAN ORGANIZATION FOR NUCLEAR RESEARCH (CERN)

ABSTRACT

Norwegian participation and contribution to the foundation of European science. The key figures in the development of the largest laboratory for particle physics in the world. Their legacy in particle accelerator application in radiotherapy.

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1. Presentation of the Semester Assignment

1.1 Introduction

My family and me has moved to Geneva area in 2016 due to my husband's position at The European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN). I have become very interested in CERN because of its sophisticated science and technology as well as due to its impact on other industries and society as such. I have particularly become interested in why Norway became and still is a CERN member state, if there are any Norwegians who have formed this organization and what role plays the accelerator technology inside and outside of CERN.

1.2 Topic

The main topic of my assignment is Norwegian participation and contribution to CERN. I would like to look at Norway's position and the reasons why Norway became a CERN Member State. Further on, I would like to focus on the legacy of two Norwegian scientists/engineers, who are not well known to the Norwegian public and highlight their contribution to the foundation of CERN. And finally, I would like to show how one of CERN's technological innovations, the linear accelerator, has been transferred to today's medical industry.

The focus of my assignment is on two epochs, two scientists/engineers and two different usages of one technological innovation:

- 1) 1950s, Norwegian participation in foundation of CERN and the role of Odd Dahl in this development.
- 2) 1950s, the technological contribution of Rolf Widerøe; the concept of the accelerator influencing the whole world of particle physics.
- 3) 2020, the past connects with the future, Norwegian legacy beyond CERN.

1.3 The Choice of Literature

My choice of literature is very broad. To cover the early years of CERN, the general foundation of CERN and reasons of Norway becoming a founding member I have chosen to use History of

CERN (Hermann , Krige, Mersits, & Pestre, 2000) written by a study team outside of CERN, funded from institutions in several member states and led by Armin Hermann, professor for History of Science and Technology at the University of Stuttgart. Further on I have used a CERN produced publication (CERN, Infinitely CERN: Memories of fifty years of research, 2004) and study on Norwegian participation at CERN by Helge Godø assigned by Nordic Institute for Studies in Innovation, Research and Education (NIFU).

The role of two Norwegian scientists/engineers whose contribution was so major that it could not have been left out has been cross-checked in Odd Dahl's bibliography, Aashild Sørheim's biographical chronicle on Rolf Widerøe's life, History of CERN by Armin Hermann et al. and articles published by www.onkonytt.no, medical journal Acta Oncologica, Superconducting Super Collider Laboratory in Texas, and www.cern.ch.

Finally, the technological inventions of today have required online searches of CERN's website www.cern.ch as well as www.onkonytt.no and have been cross-checked with recent publications on CERN technology by Christian W. Fabjan et al.

2. Participation

2.1 European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) – Foundation and Historical Background

Transnational history of technology emerged when major technical developments did not happen in national contexts, but also in subnational and international ones. CERN is an example of such transnational project, where international linkages between infrastructures, exchanges and circulation of people, artifacts, capital, knowledge, goods, services, and natural resources were mutually constituted (Vleuten, 2008).

After the Second World War Europe had experienced a brain drain. Prior to, during and after the war many physicists and engineers directed their escape from Europe to the United States. The States became a leading country in fundamental physics, while Europe had to be built up from the dust after its devastation. During the World War II and the Cold War that followed, science received huge interest and prestige. The success of the Manhattan Project in terms of the creation of the atomic bomb and the enormous credit given to physics for the success of the Allied forces winning the war had led to increased support for basic research. Basic research characterized as pure science or fundamental science distorted the role of technology. Science had no concern for practical utility and many scientists were defending the autonomy of science (Schatzberg, 2018). This environment created positive circumstances for foundation of European physics laboratory.

Following the creation of many international organizations, the idea of creating European atomic physics laboratory emerged. The foundation period was in the hands of few people with very different background. From diplomats to science administrators to two dozen of nuclear physicists and cosmic-ray specialists. They all had one goal, to set up a laboratory with a highly sophisticated technical equipment which no country alone could manage to build, but unified Europe could.

By 1952 it was agreed on two aspects:

- 1) Decision to create a laboratory based on purely scientific nature independent of socio-political decisions.

- 2) However, the nature of the project showed an important political dimension. Being a transnational project and very expensive one, the extensive nuclear research required a collaboration among the European States.

The first official step was taken in Lausanne in 1949 at the *European Cultural Conference*. The proposal of scientific cooperation between European countries was suggested. However, the real push came from the United States. Many scientists in the US were of European origin. It was Robert Oppenheimer, who encouraged European cooperation and who suggested a joint laboratory. In Europe one of the main persons driving this process was Professor Pierre Auger assisted by the Italian physicist Edoardo Amaldi. Pierre Auger, Director of Exact and Natural Sciences at UNESCO, proposed in June 1950 at the fifth UNESCO General Conference, the counterstrategy for the US atomic program. Norway was represented by two delegates, the astrophysicist Svein Rosseland and the physicist Gunnar Randers. Their representation was significant by their professional affiliation and scientific engagement rather than by the national interests (Dahl O. , 1981). A committee was established with a goal to prepare a temporary plan for a transnational scientific laboratory, which could be proposed to the European national states. A campaign was launched to get interest for the idea of a new joint research centre.

The campaign was met with a lot of scepticism, different opinions, interests, and directions. One of the main concerns was that the creation of a European centre might weaken the national laboratories. The Scandinavian participants (excluding Norwegians) led by Niels Bohr and the Swedes were for a co-operation between already existing laboratories rather than creating a new joint research centre. Other controversial issues had risen such as: priorities in the allocation of funds, membership of the council, who could become a member, and division of power. At the end an agreement had been reached and a model of joint European laboratory persevered. At an intergovernmental meeting at UNESCO in Paris in December 1951, the first resolution concerning establishment of Conseil Européen de pour la Recherche Nucléaire (CERN) was adopted (CERN, *Infinately CERN: Memories of fifty years of research*, 2004). Two months later an agreement establishing a provisional Council was signed and the acronym CERN was born. In October 1952 Geneva was chosen as the site, among 4 candidates: Geneva (Switzerland),

Copenhagen (Denmark), Paris (France) and Arnhem (the Netherlands). These factors played the main role:

- Technical ground (size, accessibility, availability and cost of electricity and water, accommodation, and educational facilities in the region, etc.)
- Copenhagen was too north and there was a fear among younger members of the Council that Niels Bohr (a leading physicist and Nobel Prize winner from Denmark) would dominate the laboratory
- Paris was objected due to its location in a large country, which could lead to a dominant role and neutrality would be compromised
- Arnhem was strongly supported in the Council but was withdrawn only to preserve unanimity in the face of opposition
- Finally, Geneva was supported by some members of the Executive Group, and of France (second to Paris), Italy, and Belgium- the three states that were heavily advocating for a collaborative joint laboratory and who had made substantial financial contribution. On top of it, Geneva was situated in a small neutral country, where other international organizations were hosted and it had a beautiful natural environment (Hermann , Krige, Mersits, & Pestre, 2000).

In July 1953, the CERN Convention was established and ratified by 12 founding Member States: Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland, the United Kingdom, and Yugoslavia.

On 29 September 1954, the European Organization for Nuclear Research was born.

2.2 Norwegian Participation

Norway came in the process of CERN foundation in an early stage. It was director of Institute for Nuclear Energy (IFA) Gunnar Randers and "altnuligmannen- the all-rounder" Odd Dahl who were the driving forces from Norwegian side. The idea of joint laboratory was drafted by the Royal Norwegian Council for Scientific and Industrial Research¹. There were two meetings in

¹Norges Teknisk Naturvitenskaplige Forskningsråd (NTNF) utvalget

1951 to draft this idea and in 1952 a conclusion was made: Norway should be a member of CERN. The conclusion was made that it would be impossible for Norway to perform a scientific research on that scale alone (Godø, 1997).

NTNF's Atomic committee functioned as advisory body to the Norwegian Ministry of Foreign Affairs. It was strongly advised that Norway should become a permanent member of CERN. The CERN membership was promoted by the Government on 12 March 1954 and Norwegian Parliament (Stortinget) unanimously agreed on becoming a permanent member on 26 Mai 1954 (Godø, 1997).

3. Contribution

3.1 Odd Dahl, The Founding Father (1898-1994)

With only a modest formal education, Odd Dahl had a remarkable career. He was chosen in 1922 by explorer Amundsen as a pilot for the Maud Expedition (1918-1925) (Fram Museum, 2020). Dahl became a very competent instrument designer and maker. This took him in 1930s to the Carnegie Institute in Washington, DC², where he constructed, with Merle Anthony Tuve (American geophysicist of Norwegian origin) and Lawrence Randolph Hafstad (American electrical engineer and physicist of Norwegian origin), one of the first Van de Graaf generators³. In 1936 he went to the Chr. Michelsen Institute (CMI) in Bergen, where he built Van de Graafs and a betatron⁴. Immediately after the war, he became technical director for the construction of the first nuclear reactor JEEP 1 at Kjeller, Norway. Internationally known, Dahl was invited by Pierre Auger and Edoardo Amaldi in the spring of 1951 to help in the preparatory work for CERN (Dahl O. , 1981) (Hermann , Krige, Mersits, & Pestre, 2000) .

The provisional Council's main task was to appoint the heads of the four study groups. One of these groups was the accelerator⁵ group with Cornelis Bakker (Dutch physicist) and Odd Dahl in charge. After establishing the technical groups, the next major task was to decide on the design of two accelerators. It was approved that Dahl's group would make a feasibility study of a powerful proton synchrotron⁶ and Bakker's group would design a 600MeV⁷ (proton) synchro-cyclotron. Odd Dahl's group was recommended to consider construction of their machine similar

² Carnegie Institution for Science (CIS) is an organization in the United States established to fund and perform scientific research.

³ Van de Graaff generator is an electrostatic generator which uses a moving belt to accumulate electric charge on a hollow metal globe on the top of an insulated column, creating very high electric potentials. It produces very high voltage direct current (DC) electricity at low current levels.

⁴ Betatron is a type of cyclic particle accelerator. It can be used as a source of energetic x-rays, which may be used in industrial and medical applications (radiation oncology)

⁵ Particle accelerator is a machine that uses electromagnetic fields to propel charged particles to very high speeds and energies, and to contain them in well-defined beams.

⁶ Proton Synchrotron is a type of cyclic particle accelerator, descended from the cyclotron, in which the accelerating particle beam travels around a fixed path.

⁷ Mega electron-volt

to the Brookhaven⁸ Cosmotron⁹, which operated in the energy range 10-20GeV¹⁰ (Hermann , Krige, Mersits, & Pestre, 2000).

Odd Dahl took charge of the design of the proton synchrotron (PS), with Frank Goward (who built the world's first electron synchrotron in England) as his deputy, and Rolf Widerøe as an accelerator specialist and a part-time consultant to the PS group. In August 1952 Widerøe accompanied Dahl and Goward on their much-publicized trip to Brookhaven, USA. Although the idea of the PS as a scaled-up cosmotron was already agreed on, the American hosts have presented the PS group with a new revolutionary design of high-energy accelerator. It was based on the concept of alternating-gradient¹¹ (AG) or strong-focusing principle. Applying the AG principle would considerably reduce the cost/GeV of a proton synchrotron. With this new accelerator technology in mind, the group returned to Europe determined to research the feasibility of a new concept. Even though their original design was already produced, they decided to proceed with the new principle. Odd Dahl presented their proposal to the Council session in Amsterdam in October 1952. The design energy of a new accelerator would increase to 30GeV, construction time would be reduced by 1 year and the cost would be 'not more than the other machine'. The Council trusted Dahl and agreed to abandon the original design and implement the new principle. The achievement of Odd Dahl and his group was of enormous importance. The energy range was revolutionary, technically nothing like that had been designed or built yet and Europe would reclaim its leading position in nuclear physics (Hermann , Krige, Mersits, & Pestre, 2000).

Odd Dahl reflects on this occasion in his book that his main contribution to CERN was made at the Council meeting. With his team he was able to get the Council to believe in their proposition and the Council was willing to take a chance and go ahead with this project. He thinks that if the

⁸ Brookhaven National Laboratory specializes in nuclear and high energy physics, energy science and technology, environmental and bioscience, nanoscience, and national security.

⁹ Cosmotron was a particle accelerator, specifically a proton synchrotron, at Brookhaven National Laboratory.

¹⁰ Giga electron-volt

¹¹ Alternating-gradient focusing (Strong focusing) is the principle that the net effect on a particle beam of charged particles passing through alternating field gradients is to make the beam converge. By contrast, weak focusing is the principle that nearby circles, described by charged particles moving in a uniform magnetic field, only intersect once per revolution.

project had been a failure or the Council rejected the proposition, it would have had major consequences for European nuclear physics (Dahl O. , 1981).

The Proton Synchrotron (PS) is operational to this day. From being a first synchrotron in the CERN's history, and the world's largest at the time of its construction, to a driving horse for newer accelerators, today's role of PS is to supply the accelerating particles to the larger accelerators such as Super Proton Synchrotron (SPS)¹² and Large Hadron Collider (LHC)¹³

3.2 Rold Widerøe, The Forgotten Father (1902-1996)

Accelerator pioneer Rolf Widerøe was born in Oslo into well-known family, but his life circumstances made him unknown in his own country. He initially studied electrical engineering in Karlsruhe, Germany, where he became fascinated by the idea of accelerating electrons. He was confident that 'it should be possible to apply the principle of an ordinary transformer to accelerate electrons to high energy by using a varying magnetic field, following injection into an evacuated, circular glass tube placed between two magnetic poles' (Brustad, 1998, p. 603). At the age of 25 he succeeded with his doctorate in Aachen, Germany with his idea of a linear accelerator, which he was able to build, but was unable to build a circular machine, which he called radiation transformer or betatron (as it was later called). Nevertheless, he managed to make several sketches which were also presented in German electrical engineering journal. In 1929 another physicist, Ernest Lawrence came across Widerøe's idea on multiple acceleration of positive ions, which influenced Lawrence to invent the cyclotron¹⁴ and awarded him in 1939 Nobel Prize in Physics for this invention (Sørheim, 2015).

To this day it is disputed, if Lawrence should have shared his Nobel Prize with Rolf Widerøe. Lawrence has on multiple occasions recognized Widerøe's contribution:

¹² Super Proton Synchrotron is a particle accelerator of synchrotron type measuring almost 7km in circumference.

¹³ Large Hadron Collider is the world's largest particle collider measuring almost 27km in circumference.

¹⁴ Cyclotron is a type of particle accelerator which accelerates charged particles outwards from the center of a flat cylindrical vacuum chamber along a spiral path. The particles are held to a spiral trajectory by a static magnetic field and accelerated by a rapidly varying electric field.

Not being able to read German easily, I merely looked at the diagrams and photographs of Widerøe's apparatus and from the various figures in the article was able to determine his general approach to the problem-i.e., the multiple acceleration of the positive ions by appropriate application of radio frequency oscillating voltages to a series of cylindrical electrodes in line. This new idea immediately impressed me as the real answer which I had been looking for to the technical problem of accelerating positive ions, and without looking at the article further I then and there made estimates of the general features of a linear accelerator for protons in the energy range above one million volt electrons (Dahl P. F., 1992).

Going back to the concept of betatron, it was Donald W. Kerst in 1941 who consequently was able to build first betatron, which, a decade earlier was presented by Widerøe. Dramatic events followed the life of Rolf Widerøe. Prior the World War II, Rolf returned from Germany to Norway and worked on electrifying Norway. During the war, his brother Viggo Dahl joined the resistance movement. Viggo was arrested and sent to a prison in Germany. Rolf was later visited and 'advised' by the Germans to come to Germany and continue his research on betatron as it could improve his brother's situation. Rolf continued his work on the betatron and built the first machine with designed energy 15MeV in 1943.

In spring 1945, Rolf returned to Norway. He was accused of the serious treason working on German V-2 rockets, and even though he was never found guilty of working on Nazi military research or prosecuted, he with his family was forced to emigrate to Switzerland to be able to live a normal life again. Here he worked for a company called Brown Boveri & Cie as Head of Radiation Laboratory, where he dedicated his life to building radiation treatment machines- betatrons.

Oslo University Hospital (Radiumhospitalet), Norway, was one of the first hospitals in Europe to receive the Widerøe's betatron in 1953. The hospital had three betatrons over the years, which were later replaced by linear accelerators (Evensen, 2020) (Sørheim, 2015).

I would like to conclude this part with the words of Prof. Tor Brustad, who was fascinated by the life of Rolf Widerøe, who dedicated his time to clear this scientist's name and to give him the honours he never received but rightly deserved:

While the rest of the world has bestowed Widerøe with prizes, awards and honorary doctorates, Rolf Widerøe, the founder of the science of particle accelerators, the man who has contributed enormously to revolutionizing radiotherapy, stands as a footnote in the history of Norwegian physics, and with a penalty notice in the Norwegian legal records (Brustad, 1998, p. 614).

4. Past Meets Future

4.1 CLIC, Flashes of Electrons against Cancer

Basic research of CERN implies large costs to the member states, which is normally accepted in the long run, if there are other benefits to the society. Technology developed at CERN has found many uses in different industries worldwide. Accelerator applications range from treating cancer, to welding, to improving material qualities and much more. When existing technologies are obsolete or inadequate, they trigger new developments and new spheres of usage. One major area, CERN plays an important role in, is the field of medicine and specifically the field of radiotherapy in the treatment of cancer (Fabjan, Taylor, Treille, & Wenninger, 2017).

At the end of the nineteenth century, Wilhelm C. Roentgen was able to record the first X-ray picture of his wife's hand only two weeks after the X-ray technology was discovered. This was the first and fastest transfer of technology from particle physics to medicine. Since that time, particle physics has contributed significantly in the development of radiation, both in terms of medical imaging as well as for the radiotherapy (Fabjan & Schopper, Particle Physics Reference Library, 2020).

One of the CERN's latest news on technology transfer is that CERN is collaborating with Lausanne University on a conceptual design of a new radiotherapy facility, used for cancer treatment. In radiotherapy, the FLASH technique is used to obtain the effect of a high dose of radiation being sent to the cancer tumor, damaging the tumor but not affecting the surrounding healthy tissue. CERN accelerator technology applied to this technique will improve its efficiency and minimize the damage of the healthy tissue. The Compact Linear Collider (CLIC) - accelerator technology used at CERN will help to transfer high-energy electrons in the treatment of tumors. According to CERN's representatives: "Particle physics sits at the interface between fundamental science and key technological breakthroughs. The collaboration between CERN and CHUV demonstrates again how CERN technologies, unique facilities, and expertise can benefit society beyond their use for our fundamental research" (www.cern.ch, 2020). Nowadays treatment requires multiple sessions lasting few minutes. The FLASH radiotherapy will require less sessions which will last less than a second. Rolf Widerøe's initial idea of accelerators, his

lifework is in a continuous development saving many lives worldwide. Today, the radiotherapy is an essential technology which covers the treatment for about 40% of all cancer patients (Fabjan & Schopper, Particle Physics Reference Library, 2020).

4.2 Norwegian Participation in 2020

What Odd Dahl once said about Norwegian participation in CERN is as relevant today as it was in the 1950s:

One can of course ask: What is the purpose, the benefit? What do these huge investments lead to? The best I can answer is that we build our society on basic knowledge with constant new knowledge. How we make use of the knowledge is a challenge for all of us. CERN cultivates the grassroots of knowledge (Dahl O. , 1981, p. 195)¹⁵

The main benefits of the membership have grown and developed throughout the decades of CERN's existence. Main reasons of continuing the membership according to CERN's website and Fabjan et al. are:

- Access to scientific and technical programmes
- Staff employment
- Career development and training programmes
- Purchasing and outsourcing from Member States
- Industrial knowledge transfer

Staff Employment

More than 17 500 people from around the world are connected to CERN. The total of CERN's employees is around 2660 as of December 2019. The employees work on design, construction,

¹⁵ Man kan selvsagt spørre: Hva er hensikten, nytten? Hva fører disse enorme investeringer frem til? Det beste jeg kan svare er at vi bygger våre samfunn på grunnkjennelser med stadig nye kunnskaper. Hvordan vi gjør bruk av kunnskapene står som en utfordring for oss alle. CERN pleier kunnskapers `grassrot`.

and operation of the research infrastructure. They contribute to the preparation and operation of the experiments and analysis of the gathered data for over 12 000 scientists from all around the world. As per of today there is a total of 18 employees from Norway, which equals to 0.68% of the total of CERN staff excluding students and fellows (CERN, CERN Annual Personnel Statistics, 2020).

Norway's Annual Contribution as of CERN's 2020 budget is 27 014 250CHF (app. 270 mill NOK), app. 2.3% of CERN's annual budget (CERN, 2020 Annual Contributions to CERN budget, 2020).

Training Programmes

In October 2017, CERN signed a collaboration agreement with the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) in training students through the CERN doctoral, fellowship and technical student programmes and for joint projects in the field of knowledge and technology transfer. With this agreement a new generation of engineers in fields of electrical, electronic, mechanical and process engineering, mechatronics, information and communications technology, artificial intelligence and machine learning will be trained.

Purchasing from Member States and Industrial Knowledge Transfer

Purchasing and outsourcing contracts with industry amounts to approximately 60% of CERN's annual budget. The CERN's Member States expect some type of return for their contributions. Links to industry are maintained via industrial liaison officers from each Member State. Another interest of CERN's technology transfer is creation of new companies. The partnership with NTNU Trondheim has led to a development of Invenio – a free open source software managing the increasing amount of digital information, which led to a fully digital library platform used by large institutions worldwide. Although the technical innovations were motivated by the needs of the laboratory, in some cases these have been transferred to a wider community especially in case of relevance for society in general (Fabjan, Taylor, Treille, & Wenninger, 2017).

5. Conclusion

CERN is an impressive organization, which affirms that European cooperation in the field of science and technology is not just possible, but inevitable for future developments. CERN was founded in time, which was very supporting of science. Its main goal was clear- to unify the European science in the field of particle physics in a joint laboratory for purely scientific research. Throughout the years, the relationship between science and technology at CERN has evolved. From a linear view of technology as applied science to a rather symbiotic interdependent model of science and technology. CERN could not exist without advanced megamachines, which the accelerator of Odd Dahl and Rolf Widerøe was and still is an example of. The transfer of knowledge and technology is another confirmation of the importance of technology. Applications in the fields of computing, environment, and medicine benefit humans beyond the borders of CERN and support the cultural impact of technology.

I wanted to throw a light on the Norwegian contribution to the foundation of CERN, as well as the reasons why Norway's participation is as important now as it was then. I hope I was able to give the readers a better understanding of what CERN stands for and showcase its impact which goes way beyond its essential research. It trespasses and unifies borders, nations, politics, and industries. It is a true transnational organization which contributes enormously to a phenomena of technology sharing.

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